

VISCOSITY OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF CALCIUM CHLORIDE AT 35°

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Viscosity and density of aqueous solutions of calcium chloride have been measured. Viscosity of the solutions obey Jones and Dole equation. The divergence of the calculated value of A (0.016) from that of the observed one (0.014) is not appreciable.

The present work is a continuation of the work on viscosity of strong electrolytes by Chacravarty and Prasad (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 479; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 1466). The object is to find out the concentration limit to which Jones and Dole equation applies to calcium chloride which is a highly hydrated salt.

EXPERIMENTAL

Calcium chloride of 'Analar' quality of B. D. H. was used for the experiments. A stock solution was prepared and its strength was determined by finding out the concentration of the chloride ion as described before (*loc. cit.*). All the solutions used in the experiments were made by diluting the stock solution to the requisite volume. The error in concentration measurement is expected to be less than 1%. Double distilled water was used for making the solutions. The viscometer was of the same type as used by Chacravarty and Prasad (*loc. cit.*). The experimental procedure was of the same type as described in the papers referred to, except that a new arrangement was made for ensuring the same position of the viscometer in all the experiments and a microscope giving a magnification of 10 at a distance of 1 foot was used for adjusting the level of the liquid in the wider limb of the viscometer. The thermostat was maintained at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.005$. No kinetic and surface tension correction was deemed necessary on account of the construction of the viscometer. The time of efflux for water was about 31 minutes. Five readings of time of flow seldom differing from one another by more than 0.2 second and two readings for the mass of the solution differing from each other by less than 0.001 g. were taken in the case of every solution. Verner time switch was used for recording the time. The error in relative viscosity (η/η_0) is not expected to exceed 0.003 in any one of the experiments.

A pycnometer of 55 c.c. capacity and of the same form as described in the papers referred to was used. The maximum error in specific gravity ($S = \frac{\text{density of solution}}{\text{density of water}}$ at the same temperature) is not likely to exceed twenty in a million in any case. The results are tabulated below. Concentration means gram moles per litre. The specific gravities have been calculated after applying necessary bouyancy corrections.

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc.$$

$$A = 0.014. \quad B = 0.034.$$

Conc.	S.	$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ (obs.)	$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ (calc.)
0.001	1.000081	1.0008	1.0008
0.002	1.000150	1.0016	1.0014
0.003	1.000230	1.0019	1.0018
0.005	1.000370	1.0026	1.0027
0.00625	1.000453	1.0033	1.0033
0.00715	1.000537	1.0040	1.0038
0.00875	1.000670	1.0046	1.0043
0.010	1.000760	1.0050	1.0048
0.020	1.001467	1.0077	1.0088
0.030	1.002270	1.0128	1.0127
0.050	1.003836	1.0185	1.0201

A and B are found out by the usual method. The calculated (0.016 from Falkenhagen-Vernon equation) and observed (0.014) values of A are in good agreement. The limit to which the Jones and Dole equation applies as shown by italics is much lower than in other cases most probably due to the high degree of the hydration of the salt.

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